

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part IV. Dioxymethylene Group in Lignin.

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By the distillation of Willstätter-lignin Hägglund and co-workers (*Biochem. Z.*, 1924, **147**, 74; 1926, **179**, 376) obtained a product which could be condensed with phloroglucinol, barbituric acid, etc., but it was not furfural or any of its derivatives. Freudenberg and Harder (*Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 582) identified it as formaldehyde and considered it as a fission product of methylene dioxide group in lignin (*Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 1760). Fuchs and Horn (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2647) got formaldehyde but were unable to accept the hypothesis of Freudenberg because lignin gave comparatively more formaldehyde than its derivatives. Phillips and Goss (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3374) obtained formaldehyde in some lignocelluloses but not in others and, therefore, regarded the presence of this group with uncertainty. In the present investigation, the problem has been studied with special reference to jute-lignin with a view to establish definitely the presence of this group in lignin (*cf. Cellulosechem.*, 1931, **12**, 263) and also to get an idea as to its molecular size from the amount of formaldehyde obtained assuming as Freudenberg does that only one such group is present in it.

In a series of papers from this laboratory it has been shown by Chowdhury and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 239; 1930; **7**, 347; 1932, **9**, 615) that ClO_2 is the mildest reagent known that separates lignin from cellulose and hemicelluloses without affecting the latter to any appreciable extent. But in the jute, thus delignified, the furfural value (as phloroglucide) was always found to be slightly less than the calculated figure, though lignin obtained therefrom gave no furfural after purification. This has recently been found to be the case with bamboo and cocoanut fibre as well (Chowdhury and Paul, unpublished paper). Jute, rice-straw, bamboo, cocoanut fibre and teak wood were distilled with 12% HCl and formaldehyde was detected in all cases in the distillate with Schryver's reagent (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1910, **B82**, 226). Lignin was

separated with 42% HCl in each case and formaldehyde could be found in every sample. As formaldehyde also gives an insoluble condensation product with phloroglucinol, the lower furfural values in delignified jute, bamboo and cocoanut fibre, etc., can now be properly explained. Delignified jute, bamboo, etc., give no formaldehyde on distillation with 12% HCl. As formaldehyde has also been found in chlorolignin obtained from jute directly or from separated lignin and purified by alcohol and acetone repeatedly, it cannot be regarded as an impurity as some workers in this field think. Freudenberg and Sohns (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 263) got it in lignosulphonic acid from pine-wood lignin and according to Kuster and Schoder (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1927, 170, 44) a molecule of formaldehyde is supplied by lignin when heated with a little HCl and β -naphthol during the formation of merolignin.

Isolated lignin was distilled with 28% H_2SO_4 and formaldehyde was detected in the distillate as the white crystalline dimedone derivative (Weinberger, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1931, 3, 365) which was found to melt exactly at 187° . The distillate also developed fuchsine colour with Schryver's reagent which is characteristic of formaldehyde only.

From HCl-lignin on distillation with 28% H_2SO_4 or 20% NaOH a distillate was obtained which gave iodoform with iodine and alkali. Hence the well known iodometric method could not be employed for the estimation of formaldehyde. As iodoform was still obtained when formaldehyde was removed by dimedone which reacts with aldehydes only, and as the distillate gave no aldehyde on oxidation with potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid, most probably it is a ketone. As a matter of fact, higher results were obtained by the potassium cyanide method than by the dimedone process. Thus, the latter appears to be the only accurate and reliable method which has been employed here all along for the estimation of formaldehyde. This method compares favourably with the other two as has been found with a known dilute solution of formaldehyde. 28% Sulphuric acid has been found to be the best hydrolysing agent. Obviously the method fails if lignin gives furfuraldehyde on acid distillation. In a former paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 397) it was shown by the author that HCl-lignin from jute after proper purification gave no furfural. Lignin was then boiled with 3-4% acid for 1 to 2 hours during isolation. It has now been observed that much of the dioxymethylene group is lost thereby. It has been possible to free HCl-lignin from pentosans by first of all washing the former free from acid and then boiling with

water until the filtrate no longer reduces Fehling's solution. The lignin thus obtained gave much more formaldehyde.

The highest yield of formaldehyde recorded by Freudenberg and co workers (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 262) from pine-wood lignin was 1.2% only. Depending partly on this result they advanced a structural formula for lignin corresponding to a mol. wt. of 2140 (in unpolymerised form). But as the mol. wt. of lignin derivatives, so far determined by different workers, lie between 800 and 1000 (Fuchs, "Chemie des Lignins," 1926, p. 178) it is difficult to reconcile Freudenberg's figure with these. The dioxymethylene group has been found to be very unstable towards acids. Thus, when lignin was prepared by 72% sulphuric acid and boiled with 3-4% acid during isolation, the % of formaldehyde was 0.21 only. It was higher (0.65%) by the 42% HCl method followed by dilute acid boiling. When the latter step was omitted and lignin was separated by 42% HCl at 29° the % rose higher, *viz.*, 0.247%, and when lignin was separated at 20° for 24 hours 2.13% was the yield of formaldehyde. It was a very light powder of pale brown colour, while deep grey or almost black variety was obtained at higher temperature and prolonged exposure. Lastly this sample was washed repeatedly with dilute caustic soda until the washings were colourless, the maximum amount was obtained (2.63%). The % of formaldehyde fell down considerably if the lignin was exposed to the action of fuming hydrochloric acid for too long a time, the temperature remaining constant.

But this figure, too, does not represent the total amount of formaldehyde, as from piperonylic acid theoretical yield of it is never obtained. Freudenberg (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 581) explained it by saying that as soon as the formaldehyde was split off it combined with the protocatechuic acid thus formed to give back the original compound, as he got only 71% of formaldehyde. This explanation does not appear to be sound for the simple reason that according to the law of mass action, when one of the resultants (H·CHO) is free to leave the sphere of action, the reaction is bound to go to completion. Moreover, it is most unlikely that in a hydrolysing medium the methylenedioxy group should be re-introduced, a process accompanied by elimination of a molecule of water. Again, by following the method of Clowes (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2842) in which the split off formaldehyde forms an insoluble compound with phloroglucinol *in situ*, far higher results were obtained for H·CHO, though both piperonylic and protocatechuic acids are fairly soluble in hot

water. It is a well known fact that phenol and formaldehyde combine at about 150° to give a resin, 30% H_2SO_4 or dilute hydrochloric acid being used as catalysts. (Bary and others, "Natural and Synthetic Resins," p. 118). Far less than the actual amount of HCHO was obtained when a known quantity of a dilute solution of HCHO was distilled with vanilic acid, and absolutely nil with phenol; with protocatechuic acid only 77.61% of HCHO was obtainable. It is important to note here also that in the aliphatic series cent per cent HCHO was obtained by Clowes (*loc. cit.*) The phenolic groups set free, therefore, appear to be responsible for the lower yield of formaldehyde and resin formation is the most probable explanation. It has been found that no carbon separates when piperonylic acid is distilled with acid, as the residue dissolves in caustic soda to a clear solution. Hence the lower yield of HCHO cannot be thus accounted for. After solubility correction, the figure for HCHO stands at 2.78% and assuming that this represents only 77.6% of theory, and also that only one $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group is present in lignin, its mol. wt. comes to 830, which is in fair agreement with those otherwise obtained. Rassow and Wagner (*Cellulosechem.*, 1932, 13, 109) determined the mol. wt. of glycol-lignin by Barger-Rast method and gave the figure as 840.

Lignins from various sources have almost without exception been found to reduce Fehling's solution. Friese (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 2538) considered it to be due to the presence of traces of sugars, while according to Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 132) the lignin molecule contained one active aldehyde group (*cf.* Heuser, *Paper Trade J.*, 1930, 88, 75; Klason, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 625). The dioxymethylene group present in lignin suffers decomposition to a greater or less extent during isolation, depending on the method employed. The two phenolic groups in the *ortho*-position, which thus result, have now been found responsible for the reducing action. It has thus been possible to separate lignin obtained by 42% HCl at 20° for 24 hours into two fractions by repeated treatment with dilute caustic soda at room temperature in a glass filter, until the washings are colourless. The soluble fraction reduced Fehling's solution and liberated silver from an ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate, just like protocatechuic acid or pyrocatechol, while the insoluble one (major portion) showed no reducing property at all. The percentage of HCHO in this rose up to 2.63%. Moreover, when all the HCHO was distilled off from the insoluble

fraction, the residue left was soluble in NaOH and again reduced Fehling's solution. The higher the temperature, and the longer the time of exposure to the acid, the less has been found the percentage of HCHO in the separated lignin and the stronger the reducing action as well.

In order to prove more directly that the HCHO in lignin comes from the $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group present in it, all the HCHO was distilled off from lignin with 28% H_2SO_4 and the residual substance was treated in a sealed tube at $147-50^\circ$ with methylene iodide and caustic potash in absence of moisture, according to the method of Fittig and Remsen (*Annalen*, 1873, 168, 94). The purified product, completely freed from CH_2I_2 , again gave HCHO on distillation with acid. The process of methylenation was repeated thrice and the final product after alkali-washing was found to give practically the same amount of HCHO (2.31%) as the original lignin and it no longer reduced Fehling's solution. The $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group has been found to be more or less unaffected during halogenation and treatment with boiling alcoholic potash. On distillation with 20% NaOH no trace of HCHO could be split off from lignin. The observations of Freudenberg and Sohns (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 262) that the $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group is decomposed by dilute alkali, could not, therefore, be confirmed in the case of jute-lignin.

In view of the fact that higher yield of HCHO was obtained from lignin separated at low temperature, an attempt was made to isolate the same at very low temperature with 42% HCl but unfortunately it was found that below 20° no complete separation was possible; a rose coloured cellu-dextrine type of substance was obtained, which gave a white powder by the action of ClO_2 in aqueous suspension. With 72% H_2SO_4 as well the same difficulty arose and even the lignin obtained at 20° had a far lower HCHO value.

So long the methoxy content used to serve as the only criterion for the purity of lignin, the higher the value the purer was considered the product. But this is quite defective as by NaOH under pressure (Mehta, *Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 958) a lignin was obtained from jute which had 20.1% methoxy value (Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 401) although it was fairly soluble in water. As the mildest procedure has to be adopted in obtaining a lignin with high % of HCHO, obviously the methoxy groups remain unaffected. As a matter of fact, 16.41% methoxy has been

found in such a sample. The $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group rather than the methoxy alone should, therefore, be regarded as the criterion. It is thus becoming increasingly difficult to lend support to the theory that pectin or hemicelluloses are the precursor of lignin. As will be shown later on, the acetyl group also is characteristic of pectin and not present in lignin.

It is interesting to note in this connection that traces of HCHO have been obtained by the author from glucose and fructose on distillation with 28% H_2SO_4 or 12% HCl. But there is no plausible ground to draw the conclusion that these sugar residues are present in lignin; because they always gave furfural or its derivative under such conditions, while lignin gave none, and secondly the amount of HCHO was extremely small being present only in the first 10-15 c.c. of the distillate and could only be detected by Schryver's reagent, while lignin (0.3-0.4 g) took about 4-5 hours to part with its formaldehyde.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In order to show that the percentage of furfural in delignified lignocelluloses is always lower than the calculated amount, furfural was carefully determined by the phloroglucide method of Tollens and Bodner (*Z. Landwirt*, 1910, 58, 232) by distillation with 12 % HCl. The precipitation was done in the cold as Klingstedt (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1925, 66, 129) has shown that better results are thus obtained. The figures calculated on dry sample are shown below.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Lignin (HCl-method).	Furfural (on raw sample).	Furfural (in delignified sample).	Furfural (calculated on raw sample).	Deficiency.
Jute	15.43%	9.54%	8.86%	7.50%	13.22%
Bamboo	27.50	14.50	14.30	10.36	15.05
Cocoanut fibre	49.50	13.53	12.50	6.31	14.58

On distillation with 12% HCl raw straw, bamboo, jute, etc., gave both furfural and formaldehyde and the former was tested as

usual with aniline acetate paper which remained unchanged by formaldehyde and the latter by Schryver's reagent after much dilution. In very dilute solution, furfural does not interfere with the test for formaldehyde.

In the estimation of formaldehyde by the dimedone method, about 0.5 g. of dry and finely powdered lignin, purified from furfural-yielding substances, was distilled at 140-50° with 100 c.c. of 28% H_2SO_4 according to Tollens' method; 30 c.c. of distillate were collected and 30 c.c. of boiling water added to maintain the same strength of the acid. It was necessary to add a little powdered charcoal (Merck's reagent) to prevent frothing and consequent overflowing in some cases. The distillation was continued until the test for HCHO was negative. 20 C.c. of 2% dimedone in dilute NaOH were added and the liquid made just acid with acetic acid. The flask was kept at 4° for 24 hours in a frigidier after addition of 200-250 c.c. of a saturated solution of NaCl to reduce the solubility of the derivative. The precipitate was filtered in a glass filter under very mild suction and washed free from chloride. It was dried at 110° and weighed. In one sample 0.2825 g. of lignin gave 0.0724 g. of the derivative, whence $\text{HCHO} = 2.63\%$ (without solubility correction). The shining crystals are extremely soluble in acetone, alcohol and benzene. Weinberger has shown that the solubility of the derivative is 0.0005g. per 100 c.c. at 19°. A similar correction has been introduced in this case also.

To see how this method compares with the ordinary ones, a very dilute solution of HCHO (about 3.20 g. per litre) was used for the estimation by all these methods. It may be pointed out here that in the iodine method, the time should be at least half an hour and not 10 minutes as Treadwell (1924, Vol. II. p. 589) says. In the cyanide method, only a few drops of the saturated solution of ferric alum should be added and not 5 c.c. as recommended by the "Official and Tentative Methods of Analysis" (U. S. A., 1925, p. 63), otherwise anomalous results are obtained in the case of dilute solution. In order to see if a portion of the HCHO is lost during distillation, 10 c.c. of the HCHO solution were distilled with 28% H_2SO_4 (100 c.c.) as in the dimedone method and HCHO was estimated in the distillate. The following table will show that concordant results are obtained in either case. The figures for HCHO from HCl -lignin are also given below,

TABLE II.

10 C.c. of HCHO soln. taken.	Cyanide method.	Iodine method.	Dimedone method.
Without distillation	31.85 mg.	30.96 mg.	30.66 mg
After ,,	31.08	30.84	30.71
From HCl-lignin	2.31%	2.60%	1.45%

The influence of the strength of H_2SO_4 on the yield of HCHO was next studied with the same sample of lignin and H_2SO_4 of different strength by employing the dimedone method. The following table will show that 28% H_2SO_4 is the best for the purpose. HCl-lignin separated at 29° for 24 hours without acid boiling.

TABLE III.

H_2SO_4 conc. (%)	... 15.71	22.19	28.22	34.57	40.35
HCHO obtained (%)	0.59	0.81	0.947	0.78	0.324

Formaldehyde was estimated in different samples of lignin isolated under different conditions. The results are shown below.

TABLE IV.

Methods of isolation.	HCHO found.
(1) 72% H_2SO_4 at 29°, for 36 hrs. acid boiling	0.21%
(2) ,, ,, ,, without acid boiling	0.38
(3) Moistened with HCl, then 72% H_2SO_4 for 24 hrs.	0.42
(4) 42% HCl at 29°, 36 hrs. acid boiling	0.652
(5) ,, ,, without acid boiling	0.947
(6) ,, at 20° for 24 hrs. ,,	2.63
(7) ,, at 4° for 10 hrs. and at 28° for 12 hrs.	1.82
(8) Sample (6) with 42% HCl at 20° for 24 hrs.	2.02
(9) Sample (7) boiled with 4% alc. KOH for 4 hrs.	1.76
(10) 72% H_2SO_4 at 4° for 10 hrs. and at 30° for 13 hrs.	0.53

The effect of the presence of phenolic bodies on the yield of HCHO was then studied by distilling 10 c.c. of the HCHO solution

with phenol, vanillic acid, etc. Table V shows the yield in the distillate. 28% H_2SO_4 was used at a temperature of 140-60° as usual.

TABLE V.

10 C.c. of HCHO distilled with	HCHO recovered	Yield.
(a) Alone	30.97 mg.	100%
(b) Phenol (1 g.)	Nil	Nil
(c) Vanillic acid (1.5 g.)	2.00	6.45
(d) Protocatechuic acid (1.5 g.)	24.04	77.61

Molecular weight of lignin.—As mentioned above the highest yield of formaldehyde is 2.63%, making a correction for the solubility it comes 2.778%. Assuming this is only 77, the theoretical yield amounts to 3.61%. Further, on the assumption that only one $\text{O}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{O}$ group is present in the molecule, 30 g. of HCHO are to be obtained from 830 g. of lignin, which figure therefore stands for its molecular weight.

Methylenation of lignin.—About 1 g. of lignin (HCHO, 2.63%), from which all HCHO was distilled off, was dissolved in a concentrated solution of KOH (5 g. in 10 c.c.) and dried at 105°. The finely powdered substance was mixed with 5 c.c. of methylene iodide (16 g.) and heated in a sealed tube in glycerine-bath at 140-50° for 7-8 hours. The light brown mass was washed with ether to remove the excess of methylene iodide and then with water until neutral. Lastly it was boiled with water and steam was passed through it to expel the last trace of methylene iodide. It was then dried and HCHO was estimated in the sample. The product was of light brown colour. The process is far from being quantitative only a small yield of methylenated product being obtained by a single treatment. The results are shown below.

TABLE VI.

Sample treated.	No. of treatment.	HCHO.
HCl-lignin after distilling off the HCHO	1	0.91%
	2	1.34
	3	1.84
		2.31
H_2SO_4 -lignin with 0.38% HCHO	1	1.003

SUMMARY.

1. The lower yield of furfural in delignified jute, etc., is due to $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group in lignin, and lowering of percentage is nearly the same in three samples analysed.

2. Five lignocelluloses have been found to give formaldehyde as also lignins obtained therefrom, $O\text{-}CH_2\text{-}O$ group thus appears to be a common constituent of lignin.

3. Dimedone method is the only one applicable in the case of lignin, this gives identical results with that by iodine or cyanide method in dilute solution.

4. 28% H_2SO_4 gives the best result for HCHO, stronger or weaker acids giving lower values.

5. Prolonged exposure to strong acids, higher temperature and subsequent acid boiling considerably lower the yield of HCHO in lignin. Best results have been obtained at 20° for 24 hours, acid boiling being omitted.

6. Lower yield of HCHO from lignin is due to resin formation with phenolic bodies and not to the re-formation of the original substance.

7. The reducing action of lignin is due to two OH groups in the *ortho*-position set free during isolation and not to any CHO group.

8. The presence of $O\cdot CH_2\cdot O$ group has been established by methylenation.

9. The mol. wt. of lignin has been calculated as 830 from the yield of HCHO, which is in close agreement with figures otherwise obtained.

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